

Original Article

Preparation of Lokta Paper Scaffold and Lokta Paper/ Hydroxyapatite Composite Film for Bone Tissue Engineering

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This research proposes to prepare Lokta paper-based scaffold and Lokta paper/hydroxyapatite composite film for bone tissue regeneration. Lokta paper is a fibrous biocompatible material resembling 3D structures of tissue that can be cut, folded, rolled, or manipulated into the desired shape. The paper scaffold was prepared using a sequential mineralization technique to deposit hydroxyapatite onto the paper. Experiments were conducted with four scaffold samples based on different incubation times and concentrations of mineralization solutions. The deposition of hydroxyapatite onto the paper was verified by Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). It was found that with the increment in the mineralization cycle, the hydroxyapatite (HAp) content increased. Furthermore, it also showed that the concentration of the mineralized solution had an insignificant effect on the deposition of HAp. HAp and Lokta paper/HAp composite film were prepared using the sol-gel and solvent casting methods, respectively. Then the HAp and Lokta paper/HAp composite film were characterized by using FTIR and XRD methods. Furthermore, Human osteosarcoma epithelial cells (U2OS) cell culture and 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay was accomplished to examine the biocompatibility of the prepared samples. Comparing the cell viability of Lokta paper scaffold and Lokta paper/HAp composite film, even the cell viability of the 1st cycle mineralized Lokta paper scaffold was better than that of the Lokta paper/HAp film. Thus, it was concluded that the Lokta paper, itself in its pristine form, had similar cell viability with Lokta paper/HAp film, indicating that the Lokta paper would be an excellent biomaterial for bone tissue engineering.

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Introduction

Tissue engineering is a biomedical engineering discipline that restores, maintains, improves, or replaces biological tissues using a combination of cells, engineering-material techniques, and appropriate biochemical and physiochemical parameters [1]. Tissue engineering is generally associated with the use of cells to develop new living tissue for medical purposes, however, it is not only limited to cell and tissue scaffold applications [2]. Tissue engineering can be utilized to treat diseases that are resistant to traditional

medications, as well as to produce natural, living, functional organs that eliminate the need for organ donors and prostheses. Therefore, their major purpose is to provide viable replacements for damaged tissues [3]. The orthopedic, musculoskeletal, and spine substitutes are the most popular, followed by skin, nerve tissues, and other organs [4]. Skin injuries can cause disfigurement and impairment, as well as more serious infections and psychological distress to victims. Because of these reasons, skin tissue regeneration was in high demand, notably in military burn wounds where skin was a critical target [5]. The ultimate goal for tissue engineering and regenerative medicine is to eliminate the need for organ transplants in the future. Thus, the ability to construct or aid in the regeneration of such organs would be a huge step forward in the domain of medicine [6-8].

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Paper is a heterogeneous mixture of plant material such as cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, etc., filler material like China clay, calcium carbonate, etc., and chemical additives of rosin, alum, and starch, depending on the paper's grade [9]. Cellulose, the major component of commercially available paper has good mechanical strength, biocompatibility, biodegradability, environmentally friendly and renewable. The paper has emerged as a promising scaffold material in tissue engineering due to its higher porosity, biocompatibility and cost-effectiveness [10]. Filter paper, lens paper, chromatography paper, weighing paper, and wiping tissue have been used in various tissue engineering applications [11]. Out of these papers, filter paper is most widely used in various biomedical applications [12]. The physicochemical properties of paper are influenced by a network of auto-adhering cellulose fibers within a network structure. Cellulose is used in different biomaterials, such as hydrogels, scaffolds, and films [13,14].

Lokta paper, a natural polymer containing cellulose is manufactured from the inner fibrous bark of Lokta bushes, which are evergreen shrubs that occur between 1600 and 4000 meters in Himalayan woods [15]. It is a highly durable material and has good resistance to tearing. Due to the heterogeneous mixture of plant materials, Lokta paper can be used in a variety of biomaterials, including hydrogels, scaffolds, films, etc. because of its good mechanical strength, biocompatibility, biodegradability, environmental friendliness, and renewability in nature. In terms of strength, it is the strongest of all papers as stated by Ilan Garibi [16]. It has a highly porous structure which is necessary for cell adhesion. The higher porosity enhanced the movement of oxygen and nutrients to and from the cells during culture, which is important for any scaffolds, hydrogels, and bio-films for tissue engineering applications [8,17].

HAp, the main component of the bone matrix, constituted by phosphates and calcium has been using as a biomaterial in tissue engineering due to its biocompatibility, bioactive nature, non-inflammatory, non-toxic, and osteoconductive properties [18]. The strength and thermal stability of the paper films improve pointedly with the deposition of HAp [19]. HAp bio-ceramic can be synthesized naturally from materials like bone, coral, eggshells, human fluids, etc., and chemically by Sol-gel method, mechanochemical precipitation, hydrothermal method, flame spray, microwave-assisted method, etc. [20]. The synthesized HAp, when used as implants, can support osteoblast adhesion and proliferation and act as a scaffold or template for new bone regeneration and growth [21].

Cellulose is an interesting choice for use as a matrix of biocomposites for medical applications due to its biodegradability and biocompatibility characteristics [22]. It has proved that cellulose-based composites covered with bio-ceramic particles improve the mechanical and physical properties of the composites [23]. Osteoconductive HAp allows attachment, proliferation, and migration of bone cells, which leads to the formation of new bone due to the variation of the calcium-to-phosphorus ratio. Thus, the biocompatibility, hydrophilicity, porosity, and mechanical strength of Lokta paper would be enhanced by the deposition of HAp.

A bone substitute is a synthetic, inorganic, or biologically organic combination that can be inserted to treat a bone defect [24]. A variety of bone substitutes have been used throughout the last 50 years. Bone substitutes are divided into bone grafts (autografts, allografts, xenografts), ceramics (hydroxyapatite, TCP, calcium sulfate), and growth factors [25]. The bone substitute must be biocompatible and not induce any inflammatory response or

inflammation. A perfect bone substitute should be thermally nonconductive, suitable, and available at a reasonable cost [26]. Fundamentally it should include important features such as porosity, osteoconductivity, bioresorbable and mechanical stability [27]. One of the key elements influencing osteoconductive is the material's porosity which is crucial for bone progress. The rate of bone integration depends on pore size, porosity volume, fraction, and interconnectivity [28]. According to numerous hypotheses, higher porosity improves osteogenesis. The greater surface area enhanced the ion exchange and adsorption of bone-inducing components [29]. The porous surface increases the mechanical interlocking between the implanted biomaterial and the surrounding natural bone [30]. There are two categories of pore size: microporous (pores larger than 100 μm) and microporous (pores smaller than 5 μm). Bone reconstruction is possible with a substantial macroporosity (400–600 μm) and appropriate macro-porosity (150–500 μm) is required for ingrowth of bone tissue [31].

Thus, considering the aforementioned biological properties of Lokta paper and HAp, for the first time, this project focused on the preparation of Lokta paper scaffold by varying the concentration and incubation time and Lokta paper/HAp composite film by sol-gel method and compared them for novel application in bone tissue engineering. Lokta paper has been traditionally used as a bandage due to its longevity and resistance to bugs and molds and also for many medicinal purposes. Even though, scientifically its application is not widely explored. The porosity of Whatman qualitative filter paper as reported by R. Bhattarai et. al, is in the range of ~64% to ~68%, whereas the porosity of Lokta paper is in the range of ~79% to ~83%. Lokta paper, as reported by G. Chhetri et. al, is the longest and strongest fibers in Nepal [32]. The Lokta paper used in this research was obtained from the fibrous inner bark of two species of Daphne shrub namely Daphne bholua and Daphne papyracea found in the foothills of Himalayan regions of Nepal [2]. Since Lokta paper was derived from the Lokta bush and not a tree, its production does not lead to deforestation, so it would be a sustainable alternative to other paper scaffolds, hydrogels and biofilms. The cellulose is a natural component of Lokta paper. The higher porosity of this paper enhances the attachment and migration of cells. The mineralized paper scaffolds can be combined with patient-specific cells and osteogenic biomolecules for bone regeneration [5]. Lokta paper coated with HAp via sequential mineralization approach is used to build a Lokta paper scaffold and find its significance in bone tissue engineering by carrying out U2OS cell culture and MTT assay on the designed scaffold. Here, different scaffolds are prepared by varying the concentration and incubation time and comparing cell proliferation properties for bone regeneration with Lokta paper/HAp composite film synthesized by the sol-gel method.

Materials and Methods

The calcium chloride dihydrate ($\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), sodium phosphate dibasic dihydrate (Na_2HPO_4), Tris buffer, lithium chloride (LiCl), dimethylacetamide (DMAc), distilled water, ethanol, (3-(4,5-Dimethyl-2-Thiazdyl)-2,5-Diphenyl)-2H-Tetrazolium Bromide (MTT Assay Reagent), dulbecco's modified eagle media (DMEM), trypsin, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), L-alanyl glutamine, phosphate buffer saline (PBS) and fetal bovine serum (FBS) were the chemicals and reagent used in the experiment.

The pH meter, weighing machine, magnetic stirrer, freezer, oven, filter paper, beaker, test tube, petri dish, falcon tube, T-flask, CO_2 incubator, autoclave, centrifuge machine, biosafety cabinet, inverted microscope, and 96 well cell culture plate was used during the experiment.

Figure 1: The general methodology flow chart

Preparation of HAp

The chemical synthesis method was used to obtain the HAp using $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and Na_2HPO_4 solution. Lokta paper/HAp composite film was prepared from the solvent-casting process. Various tests such as U2OS line culture and MTT assay were done in the prepared films to find their significance in bone tissue engineering.

First, 150 ml of 0.5M calcium chloride dihydrate ($\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) solution and 150 ml of 0.3M sodium phosphate dibasic dihydrate ($\text{NaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) solution were prepared separately. Then, 150 ml of $\text{NaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution was taken in a beaker and 150 ml $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution was added dropwise through the burette. The pH of the mixture was maintained at eight by adding sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution. The mixture was left for 24 hrs. after stirring 2hrs, to precipitate the HAp. The solution was washed several times to maintain a pH of 7.

Preparation of Scaffold

Lokta paper was cut into 2cm x 2cm square pieces. Tris buffer was prepared by adding 12.14 gm Tris in 100 ml distilled water and pH 7.4 was maintained by adding 6-7 ml concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCL). Then, $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution was prepared by adding 400 mM $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in tris buffer of pH=7.4. Similarly, 240 mM sodium phosphate (Na_3PO_4) solution was prepared by adding 40 mM $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in tris buffer of pH=7.4. The paper scaffolds were incubated first in the $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution and then in the $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution with a 1-ml solution-to-one scaffold ratio for both mineralization mediums. Complete incubation in both solutions was considered one mineralization cycle of the paper scaffolds. Similarly, various paper scaffolds were created by changing the incubation time and concentration (table 1 in supporting information).

So, samples taken out after sequential mineralization are: Sample A: A1, A2, A3, A4, A6, A9, A10; Sample B: B1, B2, B3; Sample C: C1, C2, C3 and Sample D: D1, D2, D3, D4, D6, D9, D10. Where, A, B, and C represent the 24 hrs., 48 hrs., and 72 hrs. mineralized samples, respectively, and D represents 2x concentration. Similarly, 1-10 represents the number of mineralization cycles.

Preparation of bio-composite film

First, 1 gm of Lokta powder was taken for its pretreatment. The paper was stirred in distilled water, methanol, and dimethylacetamide (DMAC) each for 24hrs. at room temperature. The treated paper was then taken and stirred in the 9% LiCl/DMAC solution for 3 days at room temperature. Then, 14 ml of the obtained solution was cast in a petri dish for 10 days.

Likewise, 1 gm of Lokta paper was taken for its pretreatment. Lokta paper was stirred in distilled water, methanol, and DMAC each for 24hrs. at room temperature. Then, 50ml of 9% LiCl/DMAC solution was prepared and 20% (w/w) of HAp powder was added. Then the solution was stirred for 3 days, and 14 ml was cast in a petri dish for 10 days. Next, 30 ml solution was heated to 150 °C and stirred for 2hrs. Then, 14 ml of it was cast in a petri dish for 10 days.

Characterization of samples

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis

FTIR provides information based on the chemical composition and physical state of the sample. FTIR analysis of HAp, mineralized scaffolds, pristine Lokta paper, paper film, and paper/HAp composite film was carried out.

This analysis was performed on 0.1gm of prepared HAp and pristine HAp. Here, pristine HAp acted as a control. Furthermore, FTIR was performed on samples A4, A6, B3, C2 and D6 using pristine Lokta paper as a control. Likewise, prepared films were cut into 0.5 x 0.5cm for FTIR test and paper film was used as a control.

X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD)

XRD examines the structure of minerals deposited on the mineralized paper scaffolds. XRD of prepared HAp, pristine HAp, mineralized scaffolds, pristine Lokta paper, paper film, and paper/HAp composite film were carried out.

XRD was performed on 0.2 gm of prepared HAp and pristine HAp. Here, pristine HAp acted as a control. Furthermore, XRD was performed on samples A4, A6, B2, C2 and D6 using pristine Lokta paper as a control.

Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

A Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) is an imaging device that gives information regarding the surface topography and composition. SEM was carried out on samples A4, A6, pristine Lokta paper, paper film and Lokta paper/HAp composite film.

Contamination test

Before carrying out the cell culture, a contamination test was performed on all the samples. To carry out this test, first, all the samples of scaffolds and composite films were cut into small pieces. Then those pieces were placed in 96 well plates, and cell growth medium (100µl) was added to it. After 24 hrs., all the pieces of samples were dipped in the medium and observed under a microscope.

Cell Culture

First, U2OS cells were grown in a 25 cm² culture flask. Then, a cell culture medium for U2OS cells was prepared. The DMEM with 10% FBS, 1% L. Glutamine, and 1% penicillin/streptomycin were used. After preparation of the medium, cells were washed with PBS (2 ml). This process was repeated thrice to remove the traces of the medium. After proper washing, 2ml of warmed 1x trypsin-

EDTA was added to the cultural flask to detach the cell. Then, the flask was placed in a CO₂ incubator at 37°C for 2-4 min. After this, cells were resuspended in the growth medium (i.e., the growth medium for twice or thrice of the trypsin in the flask was added in the culture flask to deactivate trypsin activity). Then the flask was moved, and all the cells including the medium were put into a falcon tube and centrifuged at 4,000 rpm for 4 min. After centrifuging, cell pellets were seen in the falcon tube. Then the medium in the falcon tube was removed, and a new growth medium (6 - 7 ml) was added. After this, cells were suspended in the medium with the help of a micropipette and finally, 2ml of the medium was added to three of the 25 cm² culture flask.

Seeding of cells

After the subculture, confluency of the cell was obtained by more than 80%. The two culture flasks were taken. Then, the medium was removed, and cells were washed with PBS (2 ml). This process was repeated thrice to remove the traces of the medium. After proper washing, warmed 1x trypsin-EDTA (2ml) was added to the culture flask for the detachment of adherent cells. Then the flask was placed in a CO₂ incubator at 37°C for 2-4 min. After this, the cells were suspended in the growth medium (i.e., Growth medium twice or thrice of the trypsin in the flask was added in the culture flask to deactivate trypsin activity). Then, the flask was removed, and all the cells including the medium were put into a falcon tube and centrifuged at 4,000 rpm for 4 minutes. After the centrifuge, cell pellets were seen in the falcon tube. Then the medium in the falcon tube was removed, and a new growth medium (6-7 ml) was added. After this, cells were suspended in the medium with the help of a micropipette. Then the cell counting was done using the microscopic method. Simultaneously, samples were prepared for cell culture. All the samples were punched using a punching machine to fit properly in the 96-well plate. The samples were soaked in a cell growth medium for 10 mins. All the punched samples were then kept in a 96-well plate. Cells were then seeded (100ul) in the samples kept in a 96-well plate through a micropipette. After seeding the cells in all the samples, it was incubated in a CO₂ incubator for 48 hrs. Also, the cell growth medium was changed after 24 hrs.

MTT Assay

The MTT assay was used to measure the cellular metabolic activity i.e. cell viability, cytotoxicity, and proliferation. To perform this, the MTT reagent solution was made for 80 wells, and 20μL MTT reagent solution was kept in each well. So, a 2ml MTT assay reagent solution was made. For this, the reagent was first weighed, and 0.014 grams was taken in a falcon tube. After that 2 ml of distilled water was added and kept in a vortex mixer for systematic mixing. As the solution is light-sensitive, it was wrapped in aluminum foil and kept for further use. Then the medium of cell-seeded samples in 96 well plates was removed. Lokta paper film was taken as a negative control. Then, 150μL media was added to each well where the scaffolds and films were kept. After that, 30μL MTT assay reagent was added to each well and the 96-well plate was placed in the incubator for 4 hours at 37°C. After that the 96-well plate was taken out from the incubator and 100μL DMSO was added to each well and again incubated for 15 minutes. After that, the absorbance of the solution present in each well was recorded in the ELISA reader. The absorbance values thus obtained were used to calculate the cell viability (%) of the samples using the following formula

Results

6.419 gm of HAp was obtained from the 150 ml of CaCl₂·2H₂O and 150 ml Na₂HPO₄·2H₂O.

Figure 2: FTIR spectra of HAp

FTIR analysis of synthesized HAp

The FTIR spectra of prepared HAp are shown in **figure 2**. The IR bands of HAp located around 1026 and 561 cm⁻¹ are due to the vibrations of PO₄³⁻ groups [33]. The peak located at 1026 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the asymmetric stretching mode PO₄³⁻. Likewise, the peak around 561 corresponds to asymmetric bending modes PO₄³⁻. The band around 1508 cm⁻¹ is due to CO₃²⁻ ions. Likewise, the band at 3316 cm⁻¹ is due to OH⁻ ions [34]. Thus, the IR bands of PO₄³⁻, CO₃²⁻, and OH⁻ in the prepared samples are observed within the range of the IR band of pristine hydroxyapatite mentioned above [35,36].

XRD analysis of synthesized HAp

Figure 3 shows the XRD analysis of the synthesized. Strong peaks observed at 2θ values of 26.22°, 28.63°, 32.43°, 33.43°, 34.43°, 40.24°, 47.45°, and 49.86° correspond to miller planes (022), (210), (211), (300), (202), (310), (222) and (213) respectively. These observed peaks are similar to the stoichiometric HAp characterized pattern ICDD 9-432) [35].

Thus, these obtained bands and peaks from FTIR and XRD respectively of prepared samples coincide with the bands and peaks of pristine HAp powder which confirms the formation of nano HAp [35,37,38].

Figure 3: XRD analysis of HAp

Figure 4: FTIR analysis of 24 hrs. mineralized scaffold (A4 = 4th mineralization cycle and A6 = 6th mineralization sample)

Mineralized Lokta paper scaffold

The Mineralized samples obtained from various incubation times and concentration were obtained to test whether the HAp was deposited in the prepared samples or not, and also observe the effect of the mineralization cycle and mineralization solution concentration on the amount of HAp content. The various samples after mineralization and the comparison in the physical appearance of mineralized sample are given in figures (figure 1 and figure 2 in supporting information).

Comparative FTIR analysis of 24 hrs. mineralized scaffold

The FTIR analysis of 24 hrs. mineralized scaffold at the 4th mineralization cycle and 6th mineralization cycle with Lokta paper and HAp is given in figure 4.

FTIR spectra of samples A4 and A6 were compared to confirm the deposition of HAp in the sample and the content of HAp deposition to the mineralization cycle. The FTIR spectra of sample A4 showed phosphate bands in 1027, 945, 590, 547 cm⁻¹ and A6 showed phosphate bands in 1021, 958, 597, 558 cm⁻¹. These

Figure 5: FTIR analysis of the mineralized scaffolds (A6= 6^h cycle- 24 hrs. incubation time, B3= 3rd cycle- 48 hrs. incubation time, C2= 2nd cycle- 72 hrs. incubation time and D6= 6th cycle 2x-concentration - 24 hrs. incubation time)

phosphate band ranges from 1200-900 and 620-500 cm⁻¹ confirming the presence of HAp in the sample. Additionally, CO₃²⁻ and OH⁻ bands from samples A4 and A6, aligned with the CO₃²⁻ and OH⁻ bands of HAp [33,39]. Among these three samples i.e. A4, A6, and pristine paper, the A6 showed the sharp band of phosphate group which almost fit with pure HAp. The pristine paper sample also showed a phosphate band but these bands differ from those of mineralized samples and pristine hydroxyapatite bands.

Comparative FTIR analysis of 24 hrs., 48 hrs., 72hr, and 2x concentration mineralized scaffold

Comparative FTIR analysis of 24 hrs. mineralized samples (sample A) and comparison of FTIR band of 24 hrs. (sample A), 48 hrs. (Sample B) 72hr (sample C), and 2x concentration (sample D) mineralized Scaffold is done to verify the deposition of HAp.

FTIR spectra of samples A6, B3, C2, and D6 were compared to analyze the content of HAp deposition to incubation time and concentration as shown in figure 5. The FTIR spectra of sample A6 showed phosphate bands at 1021, 958, 597, and 558 cm⁻¹. Sample B3 showed phosphate bands at 1022, 960, 596, 558 cm⁻¹. Sample C2 showed phosphate bands at 1033, 963, 585, 562 cm⁻¹. Sample D6 showed phosphate bands at 1022, 958, 597, and 557cm⁻¹. These bands were compared to the prepared pristine HAp bands which showed phosphate band range from 1200-900 and 620-500 cm⁻¹ and confirmed the presence of HAp in the sample. Furthermore, the bands of CO₃²⁻ and OH⁻ from the samples also aligned with the CO₃²⁻ and OH⁻ bands of HAp. Among these samples, the D6 sample shows the sharp absorption band of a phosphate group.

Comparative XRD analysis of 24 hrs. mineralized scaffold

The XRD analysis of 24 hrs. mineralized samples is shown in figure 6. The Intense peaks of sample A4 and A6 observed around 26°, 28°, 32°, 33°, 34°, 41°, 47°, and 50° correspond to miler planes (022), (210), (211), (300), (202), (310), (222) and (213) respectively [40,41]. Thus, the obtained XRD peaks of our A4 and A6 coincide with the pristine HAp powder, confirming the deposition of HAp in the scaffold.

Comparative XRD analysis of 24 hrs., 48 hrs., 72hr and 2x concentration mineralized scaffold

Figure 7 illustrates the XRD analysis of different mineralized samples. The peaks obtained around 26°, 28°, 32°, 33°, 34°, 41°, 47°, and 50°

Figure 6: XRD analysis of 24 hrs. mineralized scaffold (A4= 4th cycle, A6= 6th cycle)

Figure 7: XRD analysis of the mineralized scaffolds (A6= 6th cycle- 24 hrs. incubation time, B3= 3rd cycle-48 hrs. incubation time, C2= 2nd cycle- 72 hrs. incubation time and D6 = 6th cycle -2x concentration mineralized scaffold -24 hrs. incubation time)

47° and 50° of different samples correspond to Miller planes (022), (210), (211), (300), (202), (310), (222), and (213), respectively, which coincide with the peak of pristine HAp powder confirming the deposition of HAp in scaffolds.

SEM analysis of pristine and mineralized Lokta paper

Figure 8 shows the SEM images of the pristine and mineralized Lokta paper. In the figure long fibers were observed in pristine paper whereas in mineralized paper, the fibers were completely covered with HAp, demonstrating the higher amount of HAp deposited onto the paper.

Weight analysis

The weight of minerals deposited in all the mineralized scaffolds is

Figure 8: SEM image of both pristine at 50 x (A) and 1.0 kx (C), and mineralized Lokta paper at 50 x (B) and 1.0 kx (D)

Figure 9: Mineral deposited in the mineralized scaffold. (Sample A- 24 hrs., Sample B- 48 hrs., Sample C- 72 hrs., and Sample D- 2x concentration mineralized scaffold)

plotted in the figure 9. The pristine Lokta paperweight was taken as the reference weight for all samples. The weight of scaffolds of all samples increased with the mineralization cycles, indicating the HAp deposition is directly proportional to the mineralization cycles. HAp deposition in sample A and sample D was almost similar indicating that mineral deposition does not depend upon the concentration of mineralizing solutions. Similarly, HAp deposition was almost the same in samples B and C, indicating that the mineralization time of 24 hrs. was sufficient.

Lokta paper/HAp composite film

A transparent film with uniform deposition of HAp was obtained.

FTIR was conducted (figure 10) to confirm the formation of Lokta paper/HAp composite film. FTIR absorption bands detected at 3186.258 cm⁻¹ and 1552.75 cm⁻¹ refer to OH group stretching in cellulose and alkene of lignin respectively confirming the presence of paper in Lokta paper/HAp composite film. Furthermore, the FTIR spectra showed phosphate bands in 1089, 1026, 962, 632, 599, 561, 472 cm⁻¹ Thus, the phosphate band ranges from 1200-900 and 620-500 cm⁻¹ confirming the presence of HAp in the

Figure 10: FTIR analysis of Lokta paper/HAp composite film compared with Lokta paper film, HAp and Paper. Where sample C0 = Lokta Paper film without HAp and C1 = Lokta paper film with HAp

Figure 11: XRD analysis of Lokta paper/HAp composite film compared with Lokta paper film, HAp and pristine Lokta paper

composite film. The sharp absorption band of the composite film confirmed the presence of a significant amount of HAp in the composite film compared to other samples [33].

XRD analysis Lokta paper/HAp composite film compared with Lokta paper film

The X-ray diffraction analysis of the crystal structure of Lokta paper/HAp composite film are shown in figure 11. Intense peaks of Lokta paper/HAp composite film align with the peaks of HAp. However, Lokta paper film doesn't have HAp peaks indicating the presence of HAp in the composite film.

Figure 12: SEM images of Lokta paper film (figure A and C), and Lokta paper/ HAp composite film (figure B and D) at low and high magnification, respectively

SEM analysis Lokta paper and Lokta paper/hydroxyapatite composite film

SEM images of Lokta paper film and Lokta paper/HAp composite film are shown in figure 12. Here, distortion of the structure of Lokta paper was observed. HAp crystals are clearly observed in composite film demonstrating the successful preparation of Lokta paper/HAp composite film.

Cell Culture

After 3 days of the subculture, cells were observed in inverted microscope and more than 80% confluency of cells was achieved.

MTT Assay

MTT Assay was done to assess the cell viability. Here, absorbance recorded at 595 nm from ELIZA reader was used to calculate cell viability. MTT, a yellow-colored tetrazolium salt, can be reduced to formazan only the cells are viable. The formation of formazan crystals indicated the viability of U2OS cells in the samples [42].

Comparison of cell viability of all scaffolds in different mineralization cycles

Cell viability of different scaffold samples with an increase in mineralization cycle is shown in figure 13. It was observed that the pristine Lokta paper cell viability was itself ~72%. It was increased after each mineralization cycle (i.e., after deposition of hydroxyapatite) in all samples indicating the increment in HAp and the cell viability. Similar cell viability was seen in 24 hrs. mineralized samples and 2x concentration mineralized samples (i.e. samples A and D). Better cell viability was observed in sample A indicating the HAp content does not depend on the concentration of mineralizing solution. Thus, the observed cell proliferation is better in sample A than in other samples. The cell viability of the sample A was statistically analyzed through Two-way ANOVA. The Two-way ANOVA for comparison of % cell viability with an increase in mineralization cycle is given in table 3 (supporting information).

P value for the comparison between control (i.e., pristine Lokta paper) and mineralization cycle and between each mineralization cycle of the sample A is tabulated in table 3 (supporting information). P value < 0.05 has a statistically significant difference whereas a P value > 0.05 does not. Here, p value of control vs 1st mineralization cycle was > 0.05, implying that the cell viability of Lokta paper and the least mineralized scaffold is similar. Significant difference was seen in control vs the 2nd mineralization cycle indicating the cell proliferation is better and significant in HAp deposited sample. Significant difference was seen while comparing the consecutive mineralization cycle indicating the HAp content

Figure 13: Cell viability of all scaffolds in different mineralization cycles

Figure 14: Comparison of cell viability between Lokta paper film and Lokta paper/HAp film

varies the cell proliferation. P value > 0.05 was seen in 4th vs 6th mineralization cycle and 9th vs 10th mineralization cycle as HAp deposition in these scaffolds was also almost similar. The Two-way ANOVA for comparison of %cell viability between different samples is given in table 3, table 4 and table 5 (in supporting information). From this analysis, it was observed that the cell proliferation in sample A and sample D are similar as HAp deposition in these samples is almost same. Cell proliferation was better in samples A than in samples B and C. Cell viability of samples C and B are almost the same.

Comparison of cell viability of Lokta paper film and Lokta paper/HAp film

A comparison of cell viability between Lokta paper film and Lokta paper/HAp film is shown in figure 14. Here, the cell viability of Lokta paper film was 40% whereas HAp deposited Lokta paper film was up to 70%. This result was statistically analyzed through a two-tailed t-test, shown in table 6 (in supporting information), where $p < 0.05$ indicates a statistically significant difference between Lokta paper film and Lokta paper/HAp film.

Comparison of cell viability of Lokta paper scaffold and Lokta paper/HAp film

The comparison of cell viability of Lokta paper/HAp film and scaffold (sample A at different mineralized cycles) is shown in figure 15. The comparison graph shows that the cell viability of the film was even less than the least mineralized scaffold (i.e., A1). Thus,

Figure 15: Comparison of cell viability of Lokta paper/HAp film and Lokta paper scaffold (all mineralized scaffold of the sample A)

the cell viability of the scaffold was better than that of the film. This was also statistically analyzed through One-way ANOVA given in table 7 (in supporting information).

Here p-value of sample A0 (i.e., pristine Lokta paper) vs Lokta paper/HAp film was >0.05, implying that even the cell viability of pristine Lokta paper and film have no significant difference and was similar.

Discussion

Thus, HAp was synthesized using the sol-gel method which is a feasible and simple method compared to other methods, such as extraction of HAp from egg shells and animal bones [43,44]. FTIR and XRD analysis were used to verify the formation of HAp [40,41]. The major task in HAp preparation is to prepare the solution of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ maintaining the calcium/phosphate ratio to ~ 1.67 [45].

Camci-Unal et al. successfully designed a filter paper scaffold from the sequential mineralization process for inducing osteo-inductivity in bone tissue engineering [20]. Also, their next experiment found that osteoblast can be cultured in the calcium phosphate mineralized Whatman 114 filter paper scaffold fabricated in 3D shape [10]. Consequently, filter paper is being developed as a promising scaffold material because it is cost-efficient, sustainable, highly porous without oxygen diffusion limitations, and supports osteoblast growth and mineralization [20,46]. Lokta paper, having similar physical properties to filter paper and being more porous and stronger than filter paper, can be used in bone tissue engineering. But, in wet conditions, Lokta paper has low tensile strength. So, to increase its strength, bone mineral i.e., HAp was deposited onto the paper through a sequential mineralization process. Here, various scaffold samples (sample A, sample B, sample C, sample D) were prepared to analyze the deposition of HAp with varying incubation time and mineralizing solution concentration. Different characterizations concluded that the HAp content was observed in all scaffolds prepared by sequential mineralization techniques. Also, the peak intensity of A6 was higher than that of A4, indicating that HAp content increases with incubation time. The peak intensity of A6 and D6 are similar, which shows that the HAp content increment is irrespective of the concentration of the mineralizing chemical. Also, the peak intensity of 24 hrs. mineralized samples (A6 and D6) was better than that of 48 hrs. (B3) and 72 hrs. (C2), indicating the formation of HAp in the paper is better within 24hrs. incubation time. The major challenge in preparing a mineralized scaffold is to prepare the solution of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as maintaining the ratio of ca/p to H^+ 1.67 which was essential for forming HAp on the paper [20]. The weight analysis of the scaffolds showed that the HAp content increases with mineralization cycles. The FTIR, XRD, and weight analysis concluded that the HAp deposition didn't depend on the concentration of the mineralizing solutions and depends on incubation time, i.e. increases with an increase in mineralization cycles. The formation of HAp on the Lokta paper scaffold was also further verified by SEM analysis. MTT assay of the scaffold showed that better cell viability was observed in higher HAp deposited scaffold. Increment in cell viability with the mineralization cycle concluding that cell viability increases with an increase in HAp content.

Here, Lokta paper/HAp composite film was prepared through solvent casting as this method has been used widely to prepare composite films [47-50]. The major task in preparing the composite film was the dissolution of Lokta paper. Various solvents reported in various literatures such as NaOH, NaOH/Urea, NaOH/Urea/

Thiourea with different concentrations and temperatures were tested [23,51-53]. Dispersion of Lokta paper was observed when the above solvents were used but complete dissolution was not achieved due to failure to maintain a negative during the dissolution stage i.e., -10°C to -12°C [23]. Finally, LiCl/DMAc was used as a solvent for Lokta paper dissolution and dissolved after various pretreatments with distilled water, ethanol, and DMAc [48,54]. The hydroxyl protons of cellulose form strong hydrogen bonds with Cl ions after being dissolved in a DMAc/LiCl cosolvent system, breaking the intermolecular hydrogen bonding networks of cellulose and Li⁺Cl⁻ ion pairs. Simultaneously, the Li⁺ cations are solvated by free DMAc molecules, which combine with hydrogen-bonded Cl to achieve electric equilibrium. As a result, the cellulose chains are molecularly dispersed in the solvent system to form a homogeneous solution [55].

After the dissolution of Lokta paper in DMAc/LiCl solvent, two different samples were prepared. i.e., Lokta paper film and Lokta paper/HAp film. Here Lokta paper film was used as a control. FTIR analysis verified the Lokta paper film and the formation of Lokta paper/HAp film. The FTIR peaks of Lokta paper/HAp film were similar to the peaks of cellulose/HAp film [47]. The phosphate band was prominently observed in the Lokta paper/HAp film. The sharp prominent peak around 1037 cm⁻¹ in Lokta paper film depicts the C-O stretching bond structure from the functional group of alcohol (Cellulose, Hemicellulose, and Lignin). MTT assay of Lokta paper film and L.Paper/HAp film was done to evaluate the viability of U2OS cells on these samples. Better cell viability was perceived in Lokta paper/HAp film compared to Lokta paper film, concluded that the cell viability increases after adding hydroxyapatite.

Finally, the cell viability of the Lokta paper scaffold and Lokta paper/HAp composite film was compared. The scaffold had higher cell viability than the film. The cell viability of the Lokta paper/HAp composite film was over than that of the mineralized scaffold (i.e., sample A1).

Conclusions

The sequential mineralization technique was used to deposit HAp onto the paper scaffold. The deposition was confirmed by FTIR, XRD and SEM analysis. The different analyses showed that the HAp content increases with the increase in the mineralization cycle. This was also verified by weight analysis, which showed that with the increment in the mineralization cycle, the HAp content also increases. MTT assay also showed that the cell viability increases for higher HAp content samples.

Lokta paper/HAp composite film was successfully fabricated by solvent casting method and uniform deposition of HAp on the film was observed. The deposition of HAp on film was verified by FTIR, XRD, and SEM analyses. MTT assay showed that the cell viability of Lokta paper film increased with the addition of HAp. Also, the pristine Lokta paper when compared with HAp-loaded film exhibited similar viability and the cell proliferation which was ~71% higher in pristine Lokta paper compared to control (i.e., cell growth medium with cells), proving Lokta paper can be an excellent biomaterial for bone tissue engineering application.

Lokta paper scaffold demonstrated better cell viability than Lokta paper/HAp composite film. Also, the SEM image showed that the natural structure was distorted while preparing the film, although Lokta paper was in the original structure. Thus, it is concluded that HAp deposited in pristine Lokta paper through sequential mineralization would be a better biomaterial than preparing film through solvent solvent-casting method.

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